

An Evaluation of Teachers Performance Appraisal System in Botswana's Public Secondary Schools: The Case of Lehutshelo Junior Secondary School

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Effective teaching is crucial for shaping students' futures and preparing them to be responsible citizens, which underscores the importance of enhancing teachers' competencies and their ability to adapt to evolving student needs to improve educational standards. Drawing on the prediction of goal-setting theory, the study examined the components of effective performance appraisal systems as a tool for improving teaching quality in Botswana's public secondary schools. Using a mixed-methods approach, the research collected and analyzed both quantitative and qualitative data. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select participants, including teachers and senior management, based on specific characteristics relevant to the study. Descriptive statistics, exploratory factor analysis and thematic content analysis were used to evaluate the data. Results revealed that clear standards, effective communication, and active teacher involvement are essential for successful appraisals, with a supportive environment being critical for fostering professional growth. The study identified immediate supervisors as key appraisers, highlighting the need for their training to ensure fair and effective appraisals. While most participants viewed appraisals positively for personal development and performance improvement, concerns about their purpose and impact were also noted, underscoring the need for policymakers in Botswana to prioritize clear standards, effective communication, and active teacher involvement in the development and implementation of appraisal systems.

Keywords: Performance appraisal, teacher appraisal, teacher performance, Lehutshelo Junior Secondary School

In the pursuit of global educational standards, the role of teachers has become increasingly pivotal (Kennedy, 2024; Bartrop-Sackey et al., 2022; Boakye et al., 2022). Teachers with comprehensive pedagogical knowledge and competencies are essential to delivering quality education in a competitive global environment (Akintayo et al., 2024; Kalim & Bibi, 2024; Kennedy, 2024). As with other organizations, learning institutions must adopt strategic orientations to address the challenges that threaten their operations (Onyango, 2021). Within this context, teachers bear significant responsibility for fulfilling their instructional duties and improving educational outcomes (Deng et al., 2024; Kalim & Bibi, 2024). The competence of teachers, particularly their instructional abilities, directly

influences the quality of education provided (Deng et al., 2024). This connection underscores the importance of performance appraisal systems, which serve as a critical tool for evaluating and enhancing teachers' instructional competencies (Deng et al., 2024; Napocao, 2016; Timperley, 2011).

The evaluation of teachers' performance appraisal systems is not only critical for improving educational outcomes but also directly aligns with the global agenda for sustainable development, particularly Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 4, aimed at ensuring good education for all people (UNESCO, 2016). By promoting instructional competency through effective appraisals, educational institutions contribute to the development of skilled and qualified teachers, a cornerstone of SDG 4 (UNICEF, 2021). Additionally, these appraisal systems support other related goals, such as SDG 8, which emphasizes decent work and economic growth by fostering professional development and career progression for teachers (UN General Assembly, 2015). The continuous improvement of teacher performance through well-structured appraisals can therefore be seen as an integral part of advancing the quality of education and sustainable development in Botswana, ensuring that teachers are better equipped to provide quality education, which is key to achieving these global targets (UNESCO, 2017).

Recognizing this, the Botswana Ministry of Education and Skills Development (MESD) introduced guidelines aimed at promoting teacher principles, assessment, and competencies (Kabir, 2024). In 1992, the Teacher Performance Appraisal (Form TMS 3/4) was introduced to provide a comprehensive and supportive evaluation

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process for teachers (Motswakae, 1990). This system aimed to foster professional growth by ensuring that appraisals were conducted in a transparent and non-threatening manner (Monyatsi, Steyn & Kamper, 2006). It established key conditions: the appraisal system would not be used for disciplinary action, appraisees would have full access to the process, and all participants would receive training to facilitate fair assessments (Kabir, 2024; Monyatsi, Steyn, & Kamper, 2006).

Despite these initiatives, challenges persisted in the effective implementation of performance appraisals (Monyatsi, 2006). Various reforms, such as the introduction of parallel progression, job evaluation, and the Work Improvement Teams (WITS), were implemented to improve teacher performance but yielded limited success (Pheko, 2013). In response, the government of Botswana launched the Performance Management and Development (PMD) system, alongside related reforms like personnel management system digitization and human resource development (Motswakae, 1990). The PMD was introduced as a tool to enhance public service performance, with a specific focus on teachers' professional development and growth (Motswakae, 1990).

The introduction of the performance-based reward system (PBRs) marked a further evolution in teacher appraisals, shifting the focus from mere scoring to developmental activities aimed at improving performance (Moswela, 2010; Moswela, 2014). However, despite these efforts, the quality of education in Botswana, particularly at the junior secondary level, has remained a concern (Moswela, 2014). The persistent underperformance in Junior Certificate examinations has called into question the efficacy of appraisal techniques, with little evidence that excelling teachers are consistently rewarded through progression or promotion (RNPE, 1994). In light of these challenges, this study evaluates the effectiveness of the teachers' performance appraisal system used at Lehutshelo Junior Secondary School. By examining the impact of appraisals on teacher performance and the overall quality of education, this research seeks to provide insights into how performance management systems can better support instructional competency and educational outcomes. These insights are critical to Botswana's quest to achieve the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals, particularly SDG 4, which aims to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education (UNICEF, 2021). Improving teacher performance through effective appraisal systems is essential to enhancing the quality of education in the country, which directly contributes to the nation's broader sustainable development efforts, including fostering economic growth and promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all (SDG 8) (UNESCO, 2017). Based on these, three specific research objectives were formulated to guide the trajectory of the study and they include:

- To identify the conditions that facilitate effective teacher appraisals in junior secondary schools in Botswana.
- To develop procedures to facilitate effective appraisal of teachers in junior secondary schools in Botswana.
- To assess the effectiveness of the procedures and mechanisms of the present appraisal system in facilitating teacher performance

Review of Literature

Drawing on the predictions of goal-setting theory (Locke & Latham, 2002) this study highlights how an effective performance appraisal system can improve secondary school teachers' performance in

Botswana. Human behavior is motivated by the pursuit of specific, conscious goals, and that performance improves when individuals recognize and address current inadequacies as the theory states (Asiago & Gathii, 2014). In the context of teacher appraisals, the theory suggests that simply establishing goals is insufficient; a well-structured system is needed to guide teachers' actions and behaviors towards meaningful improvement (Jordan & Nasis, 2012). Armstrong (2013) further emphasizes that clear and challenging goals are key drivers of enhanced performance.

In Botswana's educational system, applying goal-setting theory is crucial for evaluating teacher performance. The appraisal system must integrate well-defined objectives to assess how effectively teachers meet these targets. This approach involves not only setting specific goals but also implementing a feedback mechanism to support continuous development. Werunga (2014) highlights that feedback should be constructive and aimed at addressing performance gaps. By utilizing goal-setting theory, the study aims to explore how well-defined goals and structured feedback contribute to improving teacher performance and development within Botswana's appraisal system, aligning with the belief that performance shortcomings can be addressed through targeted professional development.

Armstrong (2013) describes performance appraisal systems as structured methods for evaluating employee performance over a set period, typically annually. In Botswana's public service, such systems are integrated with performance-based incentives (Kabir, 2024) involving quarterly evaluations to assess progress towards goals and assign performance ratings. Effective appraisal systems should include continuous evaluation, reduce procedural complexity, and emphasize developmental feedback over punitive measures (Wendy & Mullins, 2020). Muli (2021) underscores the importance of consistent feedback for maintaining motivation and ensuring employees are aware of their performance status, which aids in identifying strengths and areas for improvement, fostering professional growth.

To be effective, a performance appraisal system must adhere to specific procedures and features. Wendy and Mullins (2020) stress that these systems are vital for identifying training needs and enhancing employee competencies. Essential elements include establishing clear performance standards, measuring actual performance, and engaging in discussions about appraisal outcomes (DeNisi & Murphy, 2017). The system should be straightforward, with well-defined criteria communicated effectively to both supervisors and employees (Armstrong, 2013). Objective measures, such as productivity and attendance, should be complemented by subjective evaluations to provide a comprehensive view of performance (Locke & Latham, 2002). Additionally, the system should facilitate open dialogue, enable the identification of corrective actions and support continuous development (DeNisi & Murphy, 2017). This holistic approach ensures that performance appraisals contribute meaningfully to professional growth and organizational effectiveness (Kennedy, 2024).

Professional learning is essential for enhancing teachers' skills and achieving their goals (Desimone & Garet, 2015). Effective professional learning involves a continuous, school-based process directly linked to teachers' daily work, rather than fragmented, isolated workshops (Isore, 2009). This ongoing development helps increase teachers' expertise and improve instructional quality, which can boost student achievement, though linking these outcomes

directly to professional learning can be challenging (Desimone & Garet, 2015). Educational policy now emphasizes professional learning as critical for improving teaching practices (OECD, 2013). Feedback and review are crucial in this process, involving both formal and informal assessments (Campion, Campion, & Campion, 2015). Providing teachers with written feedback and setting new objectives for future review cycles are vital for their professional growth (Campion, Campion, & Campion, 2015). The 2009 TALIS report indicates that effective feedback enhances job satisfaction and training, although Goddard and Emerson (1995) note that constructive critique from experienced colleagues is not always prevalent. Aligning performance evaluations with professional development needs is essential to support teachers effectively, ensuring that feedback is actionable and linked to clear standards and objectives (Napocao, 2016).

Empirical studies offer further insights into performance appraisal systems. Monyatsi, Steyn, and Kamper (2006) analyzed teacher evaluation in Botswana's secondary schools, identifying themes such as performance, motivation, and control, and revealing concerns about the system's perceived purposelessness and misuse for control. They highlighted the need for clearer communication of appraisal objectives to reduce dissatisfaction. Building on this, Monyatsi (2009) examined processes and guidelines, including Form TSM 34 and appeals procedures, revealing issues like inadequate training and misalignment between appraisers and appraisees. However, this study did not address the impact of appraisals on teacher performance a gap that this research aims to fill.

Bartlett (2001) explored perceptions of the appraisal scheme's purpose and effectiveness among various stakeholders in Botswana. The study criticized the bureaucratic, top-down approach, highlighting limitations such as unreliable rating scales, privacy issues, and incomplete evaluation processes. While acknowledging the need for assessments, concerns about fairness and effectiveness were expressed. This study is relevant as it outlines current appraisal practices and challenges in Botswana, identifying gaps that this research seeks to address.

Okemwa (2017) investigated the impact of performance reviews on teachers in Kenyan public secondary schools, finding the feedback system efficient with positive responses regarding feedback frequency and effectiveness. Teachers felt that feedback helped identify strengths and weaknesses and supported administrative decision-making. However, this study did not explore specific procedures for effective appraisal or gather learner perspectives, which this research intends to address.

Elliott (2015) examined the dual focus of performance appraisal on performance and development within Australia's National Performance and Development Framework. The study categorized research into three areas: impact on student learning, teachers' perceptions of the process, and conditions for successful appraisals. Mixed results were found regarding the correlation between evaluations and student outcomes due to inconsistent ratings and attribution challenges. The OECD identified key components for successful appraisals, including teacher involvement and trust in the process. This comparative analysis of performance appraisal practices between Australia and Botswana provides relevant insights into factors influencing appraisal effectiveness.

These studies highlight the complexity of performance appraisals

and the necessity for systems that address both practical and developmental needs of teachers. They show that effective appraisals require clear communication, continuous feedback, and alignment with professional development goals. The comparative analysis across Botswana, Kenya, and Australia indicates that while challenges are common, effective practices vary by context. This underscores the need to tailor appraisal systems to each setting's unique needs.

Participants: Provide details about the sample size, demographic characteristics, and inclusion/exclusion criteria.

Measure: Clearly describe the tools, instruments, or scales used, along with their validity and reliability.

Statistical Analysis: Explain the statistical methods and software used for data analysis.

Procedure: Outline the steps taken during data collection and processing

Method

Participants

Purposive non-probability sampling was employed to select eight administrative staff for the qualitative study, while 24 teachers participated in the quantitative study, focusing on those most likely to offer valuable insights for the study.

Measure

This study employed a mixed-methods approach, integrating both quantitative (questionnaire) and qualitative (interviews) data gathering techniques. A Likert-scale questionnaire was put into use as responses were gathered from teachers, while structured interviews provided in-depth insights from both teachers and school supervisors, also known as the School Management Team (SMT). The combination of these methods allowed for a comprehensive understanding of teacher appraisals by blending statistical analysis with detailed exploration of participants' attitudes and experiences (Sekaran & Bougie, 2019). Triangulation was employed to ensure reliability and complementarity of the data (Archibald, 2016).

The research, a single-school case study, focused on examining the impact of teacher appraisals in Hukuntsi, Botswana. This case study approach enabled an in-depth analysis within a specific context, aligning with Yin's (2014) framework for investigating real-life phenomena. A cross-sectional time horizon was adopted, offering a cost-effective and time-efficient way to gather data from multiple individuals at a single point in time (Addai et al., 2022).

Data Collection and Analysis

Data collection involved both quantitative and qualitative methods. Questionnaires with closed ended questions on a 5-point Likert scale ensured efficiency and anonymity, while in-depth interviews allowed for deeper exploration of individual perspectives (Sekaran & Bougie, 2019). Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and factor analysis, with eigenvalues guiding the retention of factors (Field, 2018). Qualitative interview data were analyzed through content analysis to identify recurring themes (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The integration of these analytical tools provided detailed understanding concerning factors influencing teacher appraisal and conditions in Botswana.

Results

The gathered quantitative data were analysed using descriptive statistics and exploratory factor analysis, while the qualitative data were assessed through thematic content analysis. The qualitative findings were then integrated with the quantitative results to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research questions and factors influencing the teacher appraisal system in Botswana's public secondary schools. Respondents' characteristics, including gender, position, qualifications, age, and teaching experience, are presented as demographic data. This is followed by a presentation of both quantitative and qualitative data, organized according to the research objectives

Participants Demographic Characteristics

Table 1 summarizes the demographic characteristics of the 24 study participants, 54% were male, while among the 8 respondents to the interview guide, 50% were male. The majority of study respondents (42%) were between the ages of 36-40 years, with those under 36 years and those over 40 years representing roughly 29% each. All of the interviewees were over 40 years old. Half of the survey participants held a diploma in secondary education, followed by 25% had a bachelor's degree, and 8.3% with a master's degree. Among the interview guide respondents, 50% had a postgraduate diploma. Most participants (54%) had over 10 years of teaching experience, and this was also true for all respondents in the interview. In terms of employment roles, 46% of survey participants were teachers, 37.5% were senior teachers (grades 1 & 2), and 16.7% were assistant teachers. The majority of interview respondents were senior teachers in grade 1 (62.5%), with one respondent each serving as head of department, deputy school head, and head teacher. The foregoing characteristics of the respondents suggest that they have a wealth of experience on teacher appraisal system in Botswana's public secondary schools and could contribute immensely to the topic study.

Table 1

Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants

Characteristic	Quantitative N=24 (%)	Qualitative N=8 (%)
Sex		
Male	13 (54.2)	4 (50.0)
Female	11 (45.8)	4 (50.0)
Age in years		
<36	7 (29.2)	
36-40	10 (41.7)	
40+	7 (29.2)	8 (100.0)
Highest professional qualification		
Diploma in Secondary Education	12 (50.0)	2 (25.0)
Bachelor of Education	6 (25.0)	2 (25.0)
Masters degree	2 (8.3)	
Postgraduate diploma in education	4 (16.7)	4 (50.0)
Work experience in years		
<10	11 (45.8)	
10+	13 (54.2)	8 (100.0)
Post presently held		
Assistant teacher	4 (16.7)	
Teacher	11 (45.8)	
Senior teacher	9 (37.5)	5 (62.5)

HOD	1 (12.5)
Deputy School Head	1 (12.5)
School head	1 (12.5)

Note. Source: Field construct, 2025

Reliability and Validity

The reliability of the data collection instrument was assessed using Cronbach's alpha (α) to test internal consistency (Robinson et al., 1991) while the average variance extracted (AVE) method was employed to evaluate validity (Bagozzi & Yi, 2012). Table 2 presents the results, indicating internal consistency for the constructs, including procedure ($\alpha = 0.70$), conditions ($\alpha = 0.832$), effectiveness ($\alpha = 0.889$), and overall items ($\alpha = 0.857$), all surpassing the acceptable threshold of 0.70 (Hair et al., 2010). The AVE values ranged from 0.546 to 0.697, also meeting the acceptable threshold (Bagozzi & Yi, 2012). Therefore, the instrument can be considered both reliable and valid.

Table 2

Reliability and Validity of the Data Instrument

Item description	No. of items	Cronbach's alpha	AVE
Procedure	7	0.700	0.546
Conditions	6	0.832	0.664
Effectiveness	11	0.889	0.697
Overall	24	0.857	

Note. Source: Authors' construct, 2025, AVE = Average variance extracted

Results on Objective 1: To Determine the Conditions that Facilitate Effective Teacher Appraisals in Junior Secondary Schools in Botswana

The research examined conditions that facilitate effective teacher appraisals, as outlined in Table 3. The results indicate that "setting standards" was the most agreed-upon factor, with 87.5% of participants ($n=21$) acknowledging its role in facilitating appraisals. This was followed by "teacher involvement in the process," with 75% ($n=18$) agreeing. The third key condition was "communication of standards" ($n=17$, 70.8%). Additional factors, including "teacher training on appraisals," "measuring actual performance," "comparing performance to standards," and "discussing appraisal results," were supported by around two-thirds of participants. In contrast, 45.8% ($n=12$) disagreed that "all parties understand the procedure," and about one-third disagreed that "supervisors were trained in conducting appraisals" and "teachers trust the assessment process."

Factor analysis was further employed to identify the underlying elements explaining the observed patterns in the data on the conditions that facilitate effective teacher appraisal. The Kaiser criterion was used to determine the number of elements to keep, while Varimax rotation facilitated a clearer interpretation (Field, 2018). Table 4 presents the results of the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test for sampling adequacy and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity to assess the suitability of the data for factor analysis (Field, 2018). The KMO value of 0.704 and the significant Bartlett's test ($p < 0.001$) indicate that the data are appropriate for factor analysis, meeting the acceptable threshold of 0.50 (Bernardo et al., 2012; Field, 2018).

Table 3*Conditions that Facilitate Effective Teacher Appraisals in Botswana*

Indicators	Mean (SD)	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)
Supervisors acquired training in conducting teacher appraisals	2.7 (1.3)	13 (54.2)	3 (12.5)	8 (33.3)
Teachers acquired training on teacher appraisal	2.4 (1.1)	16 (66.7)	4 (16.7)	4 (16.7)
The process involves teachers	2.3 (1.2)	18 (75.0)	2 (8.3)	4 (16.7)
All parties comprehend the procedure	3.1 (1.1)	9 (37.5)	4 (16.7)	11 (45.8)
Throughout the procedure, teachers have the opportunity to voice their opinions	2.6 (1.1)	14 (58.3)	6 (25.0)	4 (16.7)
Teachers have trust in the assessment	3.0 (1.0)	7 (29.3)	9 (37.5)	8 (33.3)
setting standards	2.1 (0.8)	21 (87.5)	2 (8.3)	1 (4.2)
communication standards	2.5 (1.1)	17 (70.8)	3 (12.5)	4 (16.7)
Measuring the actual performance	2.3 (1.1)	16 (66.7)	5 (20.8)	3 (12.5)
Comparing the actual performance with standards	2.5 (1.1)	16 (66.7)	3 (12.5)	5 (20.8)
Discussing the results of the appraisal	2.5 (1.1)	16 (66.7)	4 (16.7)	4 (16.7)

Note. Source: Authors' construct, 2025

Table 4*KMO and Bartlett's Test Results*

KMO Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.704
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Chi-Square	161.163
	df	55
	Sig.	.000

After conducting exploratory factor analysis, a three-factor

structure emerged. Table 5 shows that three factors were extracted with eigenvalues of 5.401, 1.761, and 1.092, respectively. Factor 1 explained approximately 49% of the overall variance before rotation and 34% after rotation. Factor 2 accounted for about 16% before rotation and 22% after rotation. Factor 3 contributed around 10% of the variance before rotation and 20% after rotation. Together, these three factors explained approximately 75% of the total variance.

Table 5*Total Variance Explained by the Three Factors*

Factor	Initial Eigenvalues			Rotation sums of squared loadings		
	Total	% of variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of variance	Cumulative %
1	5.401	49.104	49.104	3.706	33.686	33.686
2	1.761	16.006	65.11	2.366	21.51	55.196
3	1.092	9.927	75.037	2.183	19.841	75.037
4	0.924	8.4	83.437			
5	0.525	4.772	88.21			
6	0.457	4.15	92.36			
7	0.318	2.895	95.255			
8	0.205	1.863	97.117			
9	0.13	1.179	98.296			
10	0.112	1.014	99.31			
11	0.076	0.69	100			

Note. Source: Authors' construct, 2025

Table 6 presents the component matrix for the conditions following varimax rotation. The findings show that Factor 1 is closely linked to various aspects of the teacher appraisal process, particularly involving teacher participation, opinion-sharing, and the establishment of clear standards. This is supported by high factor loadings (greater than 0.5) on variables such as "Throughout the procedure, teachers have the chance to voice their opinions," "All parties involved comprehend the procedure," "Teachers have trust in the assessment," "Setting standards," and "Communication standards." Factor 1 emphasizes the collaborative and

communicative dimensions of teacher appraisal, in which teachers are actively involved, trust the process, and the standards are well conveyed. Factor 2 is primarily associated with evaluating teacher performance by measuring it against set standards. This factor has high loadings for variables such as "Measuring actual performance" and "Comparing actual performance to standards." This element represents the quantitative and evaluative parts of teacher evaluation, focusing on assessing and comparing performance to predefined benchmarks. Finally, Factor 3 includes variables connected to training and trust in the appraisal process. Variables

with strong positive loadings include "Supervisors acquired training on conducting teacher appraisals," "Teachers acquired training on teacher appraisal," "Teachers have trust in the assessment," and

"Setting standards." Factor 3 captures the need of training supervisors and teachers, as well as fostering trust in the appraisal system.

Table 6
Component Matrix after Varimax Rotation

	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3
Supervisors acquired training in conducting teacher appraisals	0.372	-0.126	0.819
Teachers acquired training on teacher appraisal	0.152	0.34	0.853
the process involves teachers	0.743	0.24	0.237
All parties comprehend the procedure	0.707	0.328	0.055
Throughout the procedure, teachers have the opportunity to voice their opinions	0.861	0.177	0.109
Teachers have trust in the assessment	0.762	-0.275	0.382
setting standards	0.576	0.265	0.402
communication standards	0.725	0.153	0.463
Measuring actual performance	0.125	0.904	-0.057
Comparing actual performance with standards	0.105	0.759	0.426
Discussing the results of the appraisal	0.534	0.69	0.079

Note. Source: Authors' construct, 2025

The qualitative interviews revealed several key themes and subthemes related to conditions that promote effective teacher appraisal. The first theme, a supportive organizational environment, was identified by respondents as essential. Subthemes included a conducive environment for teaching and learning (Respondents 1 and 2), availability of resources (Respondent 1), and motivation and encouragement (Respondents 1 & 3). Fairness and openness were also highlighted as crucial for creating an equitable appraisal process (Respondent 3).

The second theme, ethical and professional conduct, emphasized the importance of maintaining high ethical standards for both appraisers and appraisees (Respondent 4). Transparency and communication were also noted, with calls for a transparent appraisal committee (Respondent 6) and the need for clear feedback and goal setting between appraiser and appraisee (Respondent 7).

The third theme, professional growth and performance, underscored the need for appraisal processes to foster professional development and academic performance (Respondent 5). Lastly, the theme of shared vision and understanding highlighted the importance of aligning the appraisal process with the school's vision and goals (Respondent 8).

Integration of the Factor Analysis Results with the Content Analysis Results on Objective 1

The results from the factor analysis and the qualitative interviews offer complementary insights into the conditions that promote effective teacher appraisal. Factor 1 from the factor analysis emphasizes collaboration and communication, highlighting teacher participation, opinion-sharing, and clear standards-concepts echoed in the qualitative interviews under the theme of a supportive organizational environment. Respondents also stressed the need for fairness, openness, and motivation, aligning with Factor 1's emphasis on teacher involvement and trust in the appraisal process. Factor 2 focuses on the quantitative and evaluative parts of appraisal, particularly comparing performance against established set norms. This is reflected in the qualitative theme of professional growth and performance, where respondents emphasized the importance of

fostering professional development and assessing teachers' academic performance. Factor 3 highlights the significance of training for both teachers and supervisors, as well as trust in the appraisal process, which corresponds to the qualitative theme of ethical and professional conduct. In both analyses, training and trust were seen as essential to ensuring that the appraisal system functions effectively and with integrity. Thus, while the factor analysis provides a structured view of appraisal conditions, the qualitative interviews enrich this understanding by offering detailed, experiential insights into how these conditions manifest in practice.

Procedures to Facilitate Effective Appraisal of Teachers in Junior Secondary Schools in Botswana

This objective sought to ascertain the mechanisms in place to support effective appraisal of teachers and the results are presented in Table 7. According to the findings, the majority of participants (75%) believe that teacher appraisals are conducted by immediate supervisors, and an equal proportion (75%) reported that "statistical reports" are utilized in the appraisal process. Additionally, 62.5% of participants agree that "lesson observation" is used as a method for teacher appraisal. Close to half (45.8%) mentioned that regional officers are involved in the appraisal process, with the same percentage (45.8%) indicating the use of "written reports." However,

Table 7

Procedures to Facilitate Effective Appraisal in Botswana

	Mean (SD)	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)
By immediate supervisors	2.1 (1.3)	18 (75.0)	2 (8.3)	4 (16.7)
Twice a year	3.4 (1.4)	7 (29.3)	6 (25.0)	11 (45.8)
By a regional education officer	2.9 (1.2)	11 (45.8)	7 (29.2)	6 (25.0)
Lesson Observation	2.3 (1.2)	15 (62.5)	3 (12.5)	6 (25.0)
Statistical reports	1.9 (1.1)	18 (75.0)	3 (12.5)	3 (12.5)
Written reports	2.7 (1.3)	11 (45.8)	5 (20.8)	8 (33.3)
Oral reports	3.0 (1.2)	8 (33.3)	6 (25.0)	10 (41.7)

Note. Source: Authors' construct, 2025

only a small proportion (29.3%) believe that teacher appraisals occur twice a year, and about one-third support the use of oral reports in appraisals.

As shown in Table 8, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test for sampling adequacy yielded a value of 0.582, which exceeds the acceptable threshold of 0.5, indicating that the sample is adequate for conducting factor analysis (Field, 2018). Additionally, Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was significant (p -value < 0.001), further confirming that factor analysis is appropriate for the dataset. These results validate the suitability of the data for factor analysis (Field, 2018; Bernado et al., 2012).

Table 9 shows that two variables were identified in the

investigation, with eigenvalues of 3.092 and 1.488. Factor 1 accounted for almost 44% of the overall variance both before and after rotation, while Factor 2 accounted for about 21%. Together, these two factors explain roughly 65% of the overall variance.

Table 8

KMO and Bartlett's Test Results

KMO and Bartlett's test			
KMO Measure of Sampling Adequacy			.582
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Chi-Square		71.518
	df		21
	Sig.		<0.001

Table 9

Total Variance Explained

Factor	Initial Eigenvalues			Rotation sums of squared loadings		
	Total	% of variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of variance	Cumulative %
1	3.092	44.174	44.174	3.081	44.013	44.013
2	1.488	21.256	65.43	1.499	21.417	65.43
3	0.96	13.711	79.142			
4	0.839	11.988	91.13			
5	0.316	4.515	95.645			
6	0.159	2.271	97.916			
7	0.146	2.084	100			

Table 10 presents the rotated component matrix for the factor analysis of appraisal procedures. Factor 1 is primarily related with a variety of evaluation methods and reporting mechanisms, including "Lesson Observation," "Statistical reports," "Written reports," and "Oral reports." This indicates that Factor 1 captures the methods used for evaluating and reporting teacher performance, with these methods showing a strong positive correlation within this factor. Conversely, Factor 2 is characterized by variables related to the conduct and frequency of teacher appraisals. High loadings for Factor 2 include "By immediate supervisors" and "By regional education officer," reflecting the key roles in conducting appraisals, as well as "Twice a year," which denotes the appraisal frequency.

Table 10

Component Matrix after Varimax Rotation

	Factor 1	Factor 2
By immediate supervisors	-0.037	0.833
Twice a year	0.712	0.007
By a regional education officer	-0.039	0.649
Lesson Observation	0.859	0.105
Statistical reports	0.664	0.443
Written reports	0.911	-0.212
Oral reports	0.75	-0.363

Respondents from the interviews were asked about who conducts teacher appraisals in their schools. The responses varied, citing roles such as management, school heads, and heads of departments (HOD), senior teachers, senior management, top managers, and school management teams, with differences in responsible parties reported. Participants also described a range of appraisal

frequencies, including "every term," "once a term," "three times a year," "termly," "rare," and "fortnightly," reflecting the influence of individual school policies and practices on appraisal schedules.

Integration of the Factor Analysis Results with the Content Analysis Results on Objective

The results from the factor analysis and qualitative interviews on the procedures for teacher appraisal reveal a comprehensive understanding of appraisal practices. According to Table 10, Factor 1 primarily encompasses various assessment methods and reporting mechanisms, including "Lesson Observation," "Statistical reports," "Written reports," and "Oral reports," all of which are positively associated. This factor reflects the diverse methods employed to evaluate teacher performance. Factor 2, conversely, is associated with the authority figures responsible for conducting appraisals and their frequency, including variables like "By immediate supervisors," "By regional education officer," and the frequency of appraisals, such as "Twice a year."

In alignment with these findings, the qualitative interviews highlighted that teacher appraisals are conducted by a range of individuals or groups, including management, school heads, and heads of department, senior teachers, senior management, top managers, and school management teams. The diversity in respondents' answers underscores the varied roles involved in the appraisal process. Additionally, the frequency of appraisals reported by participants, such as "every term," "once a term," "three times a year," "termly," "rare," and "fortnightly," reflects the influence of individual school policies and practices, paralleling the results of Factor 2's focus on who conducts appraisals and how often they occur. This integration of factor analysis and qualitative insights

provides a nuanced view of the factors and procedures shaping teacher appraisals.

The Effectiveness of the Procedures and Mechanisms of the Present Appraisal System in Facilitating Teacher Performances

The study also aimed to evaluate the impact of current teacher appraisal systems and procedures on teacher performance. The results indicate a generally positive perception among participants regarding the impact of appraisals (see Table 11). Specifically, 75%

of participants ($n=18$) believe that teacher appraisals foster personal development. Additionally, 71% of participants ($n=17$) feel that the existing procedures and mechanisms for teacher rating enhance teacher performance. The same proportion of participants agree that appraisals provide supervisors with an opportunity to exert control over teachers. Furthermore, 62.5% of participants ($n=15$) noted that appraisals lead to improved teamwork and motivate teachers. However, 25% of participants ($n=6$) felt that teacher appraisals serve no purpose, indicating a minority view of the appraisals' efficacy.

Table 11

Effectiveness of Teacher Appraisals

	Mean (SD)	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)
Improves teacher performance	2.2 (1.2)	17 (70.8)	2 (8.3)	5 (20.8)
Motivates teachers	2.3 (1.3)	15 (62.5)	2 (8.3)	7 (27.2)
Improves teamwork	2.1 (1.0)	15 (62.5)	7 (29.2)	2 (8.3)
Provides supervisors with the opportunity to exert control over teachers	2.0 (1.0)	17 (70.8)	4 (16.7)	3 (12.5)
Serves no purpose	3.5 (1.4)	6 (25.0)	5 (20.8)	13 (54.2)
Promotes personal development	2.0 (0.9)	18 (75.0)	4 (16.7)	2 (8.3)

Note. Source: Authors' construct, 2025

Table 12 shows the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test for sampling adequacy and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity to assess the suitability of factor analysis for the data (Field, 2018). The KMO value of 0.727 exceeds the threshold of 0.5, and the Bartlett's test is significant (p -value < 0.001), indicating that the data is appropriate for factor analysis (Field, 2018; Bernado et al., 2012).

Table 13 reveals that the factor analysis identified a two-factor structure, with eigenvalues of 3.092 for Factor 1 and 1.488 for Factor 2. Factor 1 accounts for approximately 62% of the total variance before rotation and 61% after rotation, while Factor 2 accounts for

about 24% before rotation and 25% after rotation. Together, these two factors explain account for nearly 86% of the overall variance.

Table 12

KMO and Bartlett's Test Results

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.727
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	116.113
	df	15
	Sig.	.000

Table 13

Total Variance Explained

Factor	Initial Eigenvalues			Rotation sums of squared loadings		
	Total	% of variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of variance	Cumulative %
1	3.746	62.433	62.433	3.66	61.003	61.003
2	1.443	24.057	86.49	1.529	25.488	86.49
3	0.408	6.807	93.297			
4	0.24	4.001	97.298			
5	0.106	1.763	99.061			
6	0.056	0.939	100			

Table 14 presents the results of the factor analysis revealing a two-factor structure related to the effectiveness of teacher appraisals. Factor 1 highlights a positive attitude towards teacher appraisals, underscoring their importance in enhancing teacher performance, motivating teachers, improving teamwork, and fostering personal development. This factor shows high positive loadings for variables such as "Improves teacher performance" (0.949), "Motivates teachers" (0.920), "Improves teamwork" (0.937), and "Promotes

personal development" (0.931). Conversely, Factor 2 is connected with a sense of control and scepticism about the appraisal process. It is strongly linked to the characteristic "Gives supervisors an opportunity to exert control over teachers" (0.905), suggesting a view of appraisals as a tool for supervision rather than development. Additionally, "Serves no purpose" (0.803) also loads significantly on this element, indicating that the appraisal system may not have a meaningful impact.

Table 14*Component Matrix after Varimax Rotation*

	Factor 1	Factor 2
Improves teacher performance	0.949	0.01
Motivates teachers	0.92	-0.203
Improves teamwork	0.937	-0.152
Provides supervisors with the opportunity to exert control over teachers	0.16	0.905
Serves no purpose	-0.378	0.803
Promotes personal development	0.931	0.045

The interview responses regarding the effects of teacher appraisal on performance reveal a range of themes. Respondents 1, 5, 6, and 7 highlighted positive effects, noting that teacher appraisal serves as a motivational tool, encouraging teachers to improve their performance, go the extra mile, and engage in self-development. In contrast, Respondent 2 pointed out negative aspects, describing the appraisal process as time-consuming, wasteful, and demoralizing, especially when the outcomes do not lead to promotions or tangible improvements. Respondent 3 added that appraisals might not effectively promote career advancement, implying that the process could lack significant impact.

When evaluating the value of feedback from performance reviews, responses were similarly varied. Respondents 1, 5, 6, and 7 appreciated feedback, using it to address weaknesses and seeking rewards for improved performance, thus viewing feedback as a motivator. Conversely, Respondents 2 and 3 expressed skepticisms, noting that teachers often undervalue feedback due to its perceived ineffectiveness or lack of impact on career progression. Respondent 2 highlighted that feedback does not contribute to career advancement, while Respondent 3 criticized the overall effectiveness of the appraisal process. Respondent 4 also mentioned that teachers do not value feedback "that much," attributing this to a lack of rewards or promotions. These varied responses depict a spectrum of opinions on teacher appraisals and feedback, ranging from positive and motivational to ineffective and demotivating.

Discussion

Evaluating teachers' performance appraisal systems is crucial for enhancing educational outcomes and aligns with Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 4, which aims to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education for all (UNESCO, 2016). Effective appraisals promote instructional competency and contribute to the development of skilled, qualified teachers, supporting the core objectives of SDG 4 (UNICEF, 2021). Drawing on the predictions of goal-setting theory (Locke & Latham, 2002) and the power of mixed methods design, this study investigated the effects of the teacher appraisal system on teacher performance in Botswana. Goal-setting theory emphasizes the importance of specific, challenging goals and feedback in improving performance (Jordan & Nasis, 2012; Armstrong, 2013). This theoretical perspective underscores the necessity of a well-structured appraisal system that guides teachers toward meaningful improvement (Werunga, 2014).

With respect to objective 1, the study on conditions facilitating effective teacher appraisal in Botswana identified several key factors. A clear and well-defined set of standards and expectations was found to be essential, with 87.5% of participants agreeing on its importance. This aligns with Armstrong (2013) who highlighted the

role of clear and challenging goals in driving enhanced performance. Additionally, the study reinforced the significance of collaborative and communicative aspects in the appraisal process, emphasizing that teachers must be actively involved. The literature supports this, with Werunga (2014) and Wendy and Mullins (2020) stressing the need for constructive feedback and open communication. Effective communication emerged as a critical component, with 70.8% of participants agreeing on its importance (Patel & Molefi, 2022). The necessity for transparency and openness in appraisals was also emphasized, as well as the importance of training and trust, a sentiment echoed by Monyatsi (2009) who found that inadequate training and a lack of trust hindered the appraisal process in Botswana's secondary schools. Furthermore, the study underscored the importance of a supportive organizational environment, which Armstrong (2013) and DeNisi and Murphy (2017) noted as essential for fostering professional growth.

Based on objective 2, the study revealed that immediate supervisors play a dominant role in teacher appraisals, with 75% of participants identifying them as the primary appraisers. This finding highlights the influence of school leadership on teachers' appraisal experiences and the necessity of adequate training for these supervisors (Patel & Molefi, 2022). This is consistent with the findings of Muli (2021) who emphasized the importance of regular feedback for motivating employees and maintaining clarity on performance standards. Additionally, 45% of participants noted that regional officers are involved, though their role is less prominent. The use of diverse assessment methods, including statistical reports (75%) and lesson observations (62.5%), along with written reports (45.8%), reflects a multifaceted approach to appraisals, a best practice supported by DeNisi and Murphy (2017) who advocated for combining objective measures with subjective evaluations. The variability in appraisal frequency, however, suggests a need for standardization and alignment with best practices, as echoed in Monyatsi et al. (2006) who pointed out the inconsistencies and procedural issues within the existing appraisal systems in Botswana.

In respect of objective 3, most participants viewed teacher appraisal as a valuable tool for personal development, motivation, and teamwork, with 75% agreeing that it promotes personal development. This aligns with Armstrong (2013) and the findings of Desimone and Garet (2015) who stressed the role of continuous feedback in professional growth. Approximately 71% of participants also believed that the appraisal process improves performance, reinforcing the notion that well-structured appraisals can positively affect teaching effectiveness (Smith et al., 2022). However, the study also highlighted concerns about the purpose and impact of appraisals. A more skeptical perspective, as captured by Factor 2, suggests that appraisals are often viewed as tools for control rather than development, a finding consistent with Monyatsi et al. (2006) and Bartlett (2001) who found that teachers in Botswana viewed the appraisal process as bureaucratic and, at times, ineffective. Addressing these concerns through clear communication and ensuring alignment with teacher development goals could boost the system's efficacy, as suggested by Okemwa (2017) and Elliott (2015) who emphasized the need for appraisal systems to support teachers' professional growth.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study underscores the crucial role of clear standards, effective communication, and teacher involvement in

enhancing the efficacy of teacher appraisals in Botswana. The findings reveal that while teacher appraisals are generally viewed as beneficial for personal development, motivation, and performance improvement, some skepticism remains regarding their purpose and effectiveness. The study advocates for a balanced and inclusive approach, integrating diverse assessment methods and ensuring transparency to address these concerns and enhance the appraisal process. By aligning appraisals with Sustainable Development Goal 4, educational institutions can foster a more supportive environment for teacher development and performance enhancement. Additionally, these appraisals contribute to economic growth and productive employment by developing skilled and motivated educators, thereby supporting Sustainable Development Goal 8.

Implications of the Study

The findings from this study have significant implications for educational policy and practice in Botswana. The emphasis on clear standards, effective communication, and teacher involvement in the appraisal process highlights the need for policymakers to prioritize these elements in the development and implementation of teacher appraisal systems. By establishing transparent and consistent standards, and involving teachers in the appraisal process, educational institutions can create a more supportive and motivating environment for teachers. This approach aligns with Sustainable Development Goal 4, aiming to enhance educational quality and inclusivity, and can lead to improved teacher performance and professional growth.

Additionally, the study's insights into the skepticism surrounding teacher appraisals suggest that efforts should be made to address concerns about the process's effectiveness and purpose. Implementing a balanced appraisal approach that integrates diverse assessment methods and ensures transparency can help mitigate skepticism and enhance the perceived value of appraisals. This not only contributes to better educational outcomes but also supports Sustainable Development Goal 8 by fostering economic growth and productive employment through the development of skilled and motivated educators. By addressing these issues, educational institutions can improve the overall effectiveness of teacher appraisals and their impact on both teacher development and educational quality.

Limitations of the Study

This study on teacher appraisals in Botswana has various limitations that must be noted when evaluating the findings. The study's limitations include sampling bias, which occurs when the sample does not fully represent all regions and educational contexts in Botswana, potentially overlooking variations in teacher appraisal practices. Additionally, reliance on self-reported data from surveys and interviews could introduce response bias, with participants possibly providing socially desirable answers, which may affect the accuracy of the findings. The cross-sectional design captures only a snapshot of teacher appraisal perceptions at a specific time, limiting the ability to assess changes over time; longitudinal studies could offer more comprehensive insights. Furthermore, while qualitative data provides valuable insights, their generalizability may be limited, as these findings are often context-specific and may not be applicable to broader populations.

Suggestions for Future Research

Future research on teacher appraisals in Botswana should address these limitations by employing a more diverse and representative sample across various regions and educational settings to capture a broader range of appraisal practices. Additionally, utilizing mixed methods approaches that combine quantitative surveys with qualitative interviews could enhance the robustness of findings and mitigate response bias. Moreover, longitudinal studies would be in tracking changes in teacher assessment views perceptions and their impact over time, resulting in a more complete knowledge of appraisal dynamics. Additionally, expanding the scope of qualitative research to include different contexts or comparative studies could improve the generalizability of findings and offer more comprehensive insights into effective appraisal practices.

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